

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USE OF
OSTEOPLASTIC MATERIAL IN SINUS LIFT OPERATION

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Abstract. The study involved 63 patients who underwent sinus lift surgery. During sinus lifting, the effectiveness of bone replacement materials Kolapol KP-3 and Ovis was assessed. A bone density study and X-ray control were performed. It was noted that in the main group using Ovis the effectiveness of operations performed over 2 years was 98.4%. The operation of intraosseous implantation with raising the bottom of the maxillary sinuses can be considered a worthy alternative method for installing zygomatic implants.

Key words: implantation, sinus lift surgery, bone replacement materials, bone density.

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ

ОСТЕОПЛАСТИЧЕСКОГО МАТЕРИАЛА ПРИ ОПЕРАЦИИ СИНУСЛИФТИНГ

Аннотация. К исследованию привлечены 63 пациентов которым была проведена операция синуслифтинг. При синуслифтинге проводили оценку эффективности костнозамещающих материалов Колапол КП-3 и Ovis Проводили исследование плотности кости, рентгенологический контроль. Отмечено что, в основной группе с применением Ovis эффективность проведенных операций за 2 лет составила 98,4 %. Операция внутрикостной имплантации с поднятием дна верхнечелюстных пазух может считаться достойным альтернативным методом операции установки скуловых имплантатов.

Ключевые слова. Имплантация, операция синуслифтинг, костнозамещающие материалы, плотность кости.

Relevance of the topic. Dental treatment using intraosseous implants is currently of great interest among specialists and attracts an increasing number of patients (A.A. Kulakov, 1997; R.Sh. Gvetadze, 2001; V.N. Olesova, 2001).

The anatomical and physiological conditions in the distal parts of the upper jaw - cancellous bone, varying degrees of atrophy of the alveolar processes after tooth extraction and a large volume of the maxillary sinuses - in most cases are an obstacle to the successful implementation of standard implantation operations in this area.

In order to obtain reliable fixation of fixed structures in the distal parts of the upper jaw, various alternative treatment methods are used. The most common technique for increasing bone volume in the distal parts of the upper jaw currently remains the operation of raising the floor of the maxillary sinus using bone replacement materials (Nystrom E. et al., 1993; M. B. Hiirzeler et al., 1997; O.T.Jensen, 1999; Ф.Ф. Лосев, 2000; С.Ю. Иванов с соавт., 2000; Т.Г.Робустова с соавт., 2000; P.Philipart et al., 2003; G.Corrente, R.Abundo, 2004).

A number of authors, providing reports on the work done, describe such complications of the operation as perforation of the mucous membrane of the maxillary sinus during surgery (F. Khoury, 1999 G.M.Raghoebare et al., 2001), early or late nosebleeds, chronic pain (E.Regevet al., 1995), and, as perforation of the mucous membrane of the maxillary sinus during surgery (F.Khoury, 1999

G.M.Raghoebaretal., 2001), early or late nosebleeds, chronic pain (E.Regevetal., 1995), infection of the sinuses with the development of serous or purulent sinusitis (A.A.Nikitin et al., 1998; J.Wiltfangetal., 2000; DoudGalliS.K. etal., 2001), penetration of implants into the sinus (G.M.Raghoebar, A.Vissink, 2003), formation of an oroantral fistula (E.A. Maloryan, 2000; V.L. Paraskevich, 2001), etc.

Thus, studying the results of implantation surgery in the upper jaw with an increase in bone tissue volume in the maxillary sinus area is an important task for further improvement of this type of surgery.

Research Objective: A comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of osteoplastic material in sinus lift surgery.

The patients were divided into the following groups:

1. Control group: 26 people, for whom Kolapol KP-3 was used as the osteoplastic material.
2. Main group: 27 people, for whom the composite material Ovis was used as the osteoplastic material.

For patients with significant atrophy of alveolar processes in the distal regions of the upper jaw, 63 internal implantation surgeries with sinus lifting were performed (10 surgeries on both sides). The combined material Kolapol KP-3 (Polyplast, Russia) is produced in the form of soft blocks of collagen with hydroxyapatite inclusions. It is easily impregnated with blood during surgery and acquires elastic consistency.

In 16 maxillary sinuses examined via CT scans 10–14 days after surgery with Kolapol KP-3, an increase in the volume of the material was observed.

Fig. 1. A dense (462 HU) cortical plate of the bony "window" (3), clearly visible above the distal implant, is turned inward into the sinus. The mucous membrane (1) of the maxillary sinus (density 7 HU) is locally thickened.

At the 6-month follow-up CT scan, we observed densification and a reduction in material height by an average of 5 mm, which is likely due to its loose structure, significant impregnation with a blood clot during the surgery, and subsequent retraction of this clot over time. The mucous membrane of the maxillary sinus returned to its initial state.

Fig. 2. CT image of the same patient 6 months after surgery.

The material's density immediately after surgery averaged 50–100 HU, indicating its sufficient softness. After 6 months, the density increased to 200–250 HU. Follow-up studies of patients over extended periods revealed that by 8 months, the density reaches the values required for implant functioning—350 HU.

After 10 months, the material densifies to 500 HU and maintains the values necessary for implant retention and functioning within the 2.5–5 year period (Fig. 3). According to CT and OPTG data, when using Kolapol KP-3 with simultaneous implant placement (in 4 out of 20 cases) and with delayed implantation (6 out of 9 cases), insufficient height of the newly formed bone was observed. In cases of simultaneous implantation, the implant apices protruded 1–2 mm above the bone level and remained covered only by the mucous membrane.

In most cases, we found that the condition of the maxillary sinus mucosa remained unchanged after the surgery compared to the preoperative state (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. OPTG and CT images of the patient 2.5 years after surgery involving the sinus floor elevation of the right maxillary sinus with simultaneous implantation. The implants are surrounded by bone tissue of sufficient density, ranging from 680–774 HU. A fragment of the bone tissue (the bony "window") is elevated above the main bone level.

Fig. 4. OPTG and reformatted CT images in the semi-sagittal projection of patient P. 3 years after surgery involving intraosseous implantation with sinus floor elevation of the left maxillary sinus. The condition of the bone tissue around the implants is satisfactory. The apex of the distal implant protrudes 2 mm above the bone level. The sinus mucosa remains unchanged.

In the early postoperative period, KP-3 is almost indistinguishable in density from the edematous mucous membrane of the maxillary sinus. However, after 6 months, the histogram shows that the material becomes denser, though still less dense than the alveolar bone. In a series of 29 intraosseous implantation surgeries with bone volume augmentation in the maxillary sinus floor region using Kolapol KP-3, early postoperative complications were observed in 8 cases (27.5%). The most common complications included nasal bleeding, wound bleeding, and suture dehiscence in the surgical area. No adverse consequences were noted during sinus floor elevation surgeries using Kolapol KP-3 as a bone substitute material.

The most convenient material for filling the cavity formed in the maxillary sinus floor area was the composite material Ovis (Korea).

Fig. 5. Reformatted CT scan of the patient in the semi-sagittal projection. Following intraosseous implantation surgery, a homogeneous shadow of the material surrounding the implants is observed. The adjacent mucous membrane of the maxillary sinus is thickened.

The density of the newly formed tissue in the postoperative period ranged from 100 to 300 HU. The maxillary sinus mucosa showed slight parietal thickening. At 6 months postoperatively, the newly formed bone appeared homogeneous on CT, with a density of 400–600 HU. In CT examinations of 15 patients, the Ovis material placed into the cavity for bone volume augmentation generally maintained its volume. However, in cases of delayed implantation, the required bone height was not always achieved.

Fig. 6. On the SCT reformatted image of the same patient taken 4 months later, densitometric analysis reveals areas with varying density ranging from 274 to 574 HU. The sinus mucosa remains unchanged.

The density changes observed during the use of the Ovis material are clearly visible in the dynamics on histograms and density distribution graphs.

Fig. 7. Histogram of the patient after surgery. The material surrounding the apices of the implants is less dense than the bone tissue of the alveolar ridge.

As a result of the performed intrabony implantation surgeries with sinus floor elevation, after 6 months, all materials used had sufficient density for implant fixation and functioning. However,

when using Kolapol KP-3, it was found that the density of the newly formed bone after 6 months was less than 300 HU and reached the required parameters only after 10 months. Despite the similarities, surgeries using different materials differed in the intensity of postoperative manifestations, complications, changes in the volume of the material, and the resulting bone height. In 22 out of 63 cases, insufficient height was achieved—less than 11-13 mm (since in the distal areas of the upper jaw, implants of 11-13 mm in length were primarily used for proper distribution of the chewing load). Analyzing the obtained results, we found that the height of the newly formed bone tissue is more dependent on the amount of material used during the surgery than on the nature of the material itself. Thus, the effectiveness of the surgeries we performed over 2 years was 98.4%. Based on the results, the intrabony implantation surgery with sinus floor elevation can be considered a worthy alternative method to the installation of zygomatic implants (surgical success rate 97% - AI. Nawas et al., 2004), Le Fort I osteotomy (94.6% - Stoelinga P. et al., 2000; 92.8% - K. Nelson et al., 2002), as well as the placement of plate-type implants in this area (83% - E.A. Maloryan, 2000). The obtained result of the surgery (98.4%) is comparable to the results of traditional installation of intrabony implants in the upper jaw without additional interventions.

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